

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: FAUST

FIRST NAME: INGA

PROGRAM CODE: DCTD

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INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2024 on Mac Version 16.90.2)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text:

1. Structure of an Academic Essay: Introduction, Body & Conclusion (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10)
2. Multiple steps of the essay writing process (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10)
3. Cite correctly in Turabian (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 2, 41, 44)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This document is an essay about academic essay writing. Writing this is a great exercise to show that I, as a student, understand the purpose and style of the material I read and that I can put information into my own words. If I study or work at a university, I will utilize the skill of academic essay writing. In this essay, I will discuss the process, structure, and style that an educational essay must have. Surprisingly, writing is the smallest part of an academic essay. The central part is reading and gathering useful material and organizing this information. Putting this knowledge in words is the end goal of all scholarly work: creating a new source of information.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

a) The Purpose of Academic Essay Writing

The purpose of an academic essay is to present facts and ideas as quickly and clearly as possible, even if the topic is complex. I can summarize my arguments in an essay and show that I understand a topic. Academic work is about more than just gathering information. It is also about fact-checking it and thinking about it critically. Reading as

many different sources as possible is essential to gather unbiased information. Summing this information into 3-5 pages is also crucial so readers can easily understand the discussed topic. The structure of an academic essay must be quickly readable and in logical order.

b) Style and Tone

We all have a personal style of expressing ourselves. When writing an academic essay, I must turn down my style and exchange it for a formal tone. Especially as a non-English-speaking native, it can be more difficult to express myself precisely in my second language. In my MBA studies, I needed to use the third person to talk about myself as the author of this essay. Here at the EUCLID, I can speak as myself from a first-person standpoint. In academic essays, avoiding the passive form is also essential. It is better to write shorter sentences as they are better for reading and making a well-structured impression (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 14).

c) Critical Thinking and Analysis

Academic essay writing is not just about collecting information but also about critical thinking about that knowledge. I may find information or opinions on which content will vary from each other, stating the opposite of other details. As a student, I interpret and judge the reading material critically. Studying is about questioning the status quo. Even though citing information is essential to avoid plagiarizing, I can also add my opinions and critical aspects to a topic. In this way, our professor can see that we have dealt critically with the subject, and subsequent students can refer to these academic summaries.

d) Essay Writing Process

The essay-writing process has multiple steps: Starting the Essay, Researching the Topic, Organizing Ideas, Writing the Essay, Referencing the Essay, and Editing the Essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 4).

i) Starting the Essay

Writing an academic essay is not strictly linear, but I need to follow specific vital steps. Starting as early as possible is essential to allow time for reading, research, reflection, and drafting, as procrastination can impact the quality of the work. Defining the question and reading the task from beginning to end ensures the essay addresses the topic. Additionally, drafting an initial plan helps organize preliminary ideas and guides further research, providing a clear structure and relevant information for answering the question effectively (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 7).

ii) Researching the Topic

After understanding the topic, the next crucial step in writing an academic essay is reading and researching to gather evidence for developing a thesis. While reading, assessing what I already know, what needs further exploration, and whether the material is relevant to my argument is vital. Taking detailed notes and recording full bibliographic details is essential. Remember the essay question throughout, ensuring all evidence directly supports my argument. I use library resources to find relevant material, skim texts for critical sections, and annotate important information. Effective essay writing combines creative thinking to broaden ideas and critical thinking to refine them, ensuring a balanced analysis considering multiple perspectives and opposing views (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 8-9).

iii) Organizing your Ideas

After completing the reading and research, my ideas will become more refined, making it the ideal time to create an essay plan. This plan will help me determine how to answer the question and structure my essay effectively. To begin, I decided on a possible answer based on my research. Next, I select the most relevant information to support this answer, ensuring I choose examples from my notes that provide strong evidence. Once I have gathered this material, I will decide on the key points I will discuss and how they will appear in my essay. Finally, I write these points in a brief sketch form to serve as my essay plan, guiding my writing process and ensuring a coherent argument (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 9-10).

iv) Writing the Essay

The first step is to create an initial draft of the raw material for further editing and rewriting. This draft helps clarify the essay's framework, organized into an introduction, body, and conclusion. Starting as early as possible reduces anxiety and allows ideas to develop. I begin with sections I am ready to write, such as the body, and save the introduction and conclusion for later. Keep the essay question in mind to maintain focus, revise thoroughly for flow and logic, and set the essay aside for a few days before proofreading for errors (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10-11).

v) Referencing the Essay

Remembering that references the response paper requires in all academic works is crucial. References are the only defense against plagiarism, a prominent academic transgression. I must discover and comprehend the journal's, schools', or faculty's referencing style. Some will offer advice on their preferred referencing style. However, other academic institutions like EUCLID will accept any reference if it follows a rigid format and is consistent throughout the work (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 11).

vi) Editing the Essay

Careful editing significantly improves essays. Setting the essay aside for a few days before revising is recommended, allowing time for reflection and a fresh perspective. I focus on the overall structure when editing, ensuring a clear introduction, body, and conclusion. Each paragraph should have a distinct main point and follow a logical sequence. Revise sentences for clarity, check punctuation and spelling, and ensure smooth transitions between ideas. Key questions to consider include: Have I answered the question thoroughly? Is my argument logical and well-researched? Is the evidence relevant? Have I followed citation guidelines and adhered to word limits (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 11-12)?

e) Structure of an Academic Essay

I structure essays in the following format: Introduction, Body, and Conclusion (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10).

vii) Introduction

From general to specific, the introduction shifts. An introduction is where I address the question with a thesis statement, give a quick overview or “road map” of my essay (I keep it brief but include all the significant concepts), and begin with a short orientation. I introduce the topic areas with one or two generic, broad opening phrases (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10).

viii) Body

I make up my essay’s body of paragraphs. Each serves as a foundational element for my argument. I respond to the query by starting a conversation in the body, demonstrating my understanding and familiarity with the content I have read (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10).

I provide explanations and supporting data to strengthen my position. I make use of credible quotations and pertinent instances. If my question consists of multiple parts, I divide the body into sections that address each of the parts (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10).

ix) Conclusion

From the specific to the universal, the conclusion shifts. It should reiterate my response to the question, restate the key ideas, and conclude with a general remark that qualifies the conclusion, discusses potential ramifications, and suggests further lines of inquiry. However, the conclusion should never include fresh material or ideas. Instead, it should serve as a summary to wrap up the essay (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 10).

f) Cite Correctly in Turabian

While other globally accepted rules are acceptable, EUCLID advises using the Chicago Rules (Turabian) (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 41).

The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (published by the University of Chicago Press) outline the format for books and research papers using the Chicago Style. Although a "Turabian style" is occasionally mentioned, this is only the Chicago style used for research papers (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 44).

The recommended citations for this course pack, following the Turabian Author-Date style, should include the author's name, the title of the article or chapter, and the course name, with the instructor listed as the editor. The publication information should include the location and date of publication, typically using the bookstore as the publisher and the semester and year as the publication date (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, 2).

In-Text: (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, page no.)

Reference List: Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

3) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, academic essay writing is the skill I will use the most as a student. A logical structure and clear language are essential to writing a good essay. Also, the planning phase is critical and often underrated in academic essay writing. Citing in the style of the university is crucial to avoid plagiarism and even failing the course. Academic essay writing enables me as a student to understand a topic and add to the academic discourse. As such, academic essays play a vital role in both personal intellectual development and broader scholarly communication.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.